

Effects of Team Sports Participation on Physical Health, Cognitive Development, and Academic Performance in Children and Adolescents

Aiden Lee¹

¹Horizon Christian Academy, Cumming, GA, USA.

Email: aidenl0330@gmail.com

Abstract

Recent research has increasingly investigated the impact of sports participation and physical activity on health, brain development, and academic performance among children. While most studies have focused broadly on physical activity, team sports may be more beneficial for children since they require communication, cooperation, and rapid decision-making. These elements may contribute not only to physical health but also to cognitive and academic development in children. However, existing studies report mixed findings regarding the effects of general physical activity, school-based physical education, and different types of sports. This mini literature review aims to show how team sports influence children's physical, cognitive, and academic development. Specifically, this review explores potential benefits of team sports participation in cardiovascular, muscular, and overall health in children. In addition, this review examines how team sports can influence children's cognitive function, such as attention, memory, and behavior, as well as, whether team sports participation are linked to better academic performance.

Keywords: Physical activity, Team sports, Health, Cognitive function, Academic performance, Adolescence.

Introduction

Participation in physical activity and sports during childhood and adolescence has been widely studied due to its potential benefits for physical health, cognitive development, and academic outcomes. Childhood represents a critical period of growth, as behaviors and skills developed during this stage can

influence their health and learning in later life (1). As a result, numerous studies have examined how engagement in physical activity or sports contributes to healthier development across the lifespan (2). However, much of the existing literature has focused on physical activity or sports participation in a broad and general sense, rather than specifically examining team-based sports. In addition, many studies have included adolescents, high school students, or mixed-age populations extending into adulthood (2), making it difficult to clearly understand the unique effects of team sports participation during childhood. While these studies provide valuable evidence regarding overall physical activity and health, they may not fully capture the specific physical, cognitive, and academic benefits associated with the interactive and cognitively demanding nature of team sports.

Team sports differ from individual or self-paced physical activities in that they require constant communication, cooperation, strategic decision-making, and rapid responses to changing environments (3). These characteristics suggest that team sports may offer distinct advantages beyond general physical activity, particularly for physical fitness, executive function development, and school-related outcomes. Previous research has shown that sports participation is associated with improvements in cardiovascular fitness, muscular strength, endurance, and body composition (4). Moreover, aside from the physical advantages, there is growing evidence of improved executive functions such as attention, working memory, and self-control (5). In fact, because executive functions are closely linked to learning and academic achievement, engagement in team sports may also contribute to improved academic performance in children and adolescents (6).

Despite growing interest in this area, there remains a lack of research that specifically synthesizes evidence on team sports participation during childhood, with a focus on both physical health and cognitive and academic outcomes. Therefore, the purpose of this review is to examine existing studies on the effects of team sports participation on the physical health, cognitive development, and academic performance in children and adolescents. By highlighting findings that focus specifically on team-based sports, this review aims to clarify their potential role in supporting healthy and well-rounded development during childhood.

Physical Health and Fitness Benefits of Team Sports Participation

Childhood is an important period for the development of lifelong healthy behaviors, such as regular physical activity through participation in organized sports (1). Participating in sports is known to enhance cardiovascular health, endurance, muscular strength, and coordination through the incorporation of aerobic and anaerobic exercises into team sports (4). Korcz and Monyeki found that sport participation in adolescents was correlated with lower body fat, better cardiorespiratory health (maximal oxygen

consumption (VO₂max)), and muscle endurance assessed by the 30-s sit-up test compared with nonparticipants (7). In addition, body mass index was reduced following an after-school soccer program in overweight children in grades 4 and 5 compared to the control group (8). Moreover, a systematic review showed that sports participation in children and adolescents was related to lower diastolic blood pressure, suggesting an impact of sports participation on cardiovascular health markers (9). Furthermore, participation in organized sports during childhood and adolescence was associated with bone mineral content at age 20 years, suggesting a potential long-term benefit in skeletal muscle in later life (10).

Cognitive Development and Executive Function Benefits of Team Sports

Engaging in team sports demands high levels of concentration, rapid response, memory, decision-making, and control abilities, which can improve the development of cognitive function in children. Executive function is defined as a set of higher-level cognitive processes responsible for selecting, organizing, coordinating, and regulating complex, goal-oriented operations involved in perception, memory, and action (5). According to De Waelle et al. (11) study, team sports athletes aged between 8 and 12 years old performed better in executive functioning tasks compared to self-paced sports athletes and non-athletes, suggesting a strong association between cognitive engagement during team-based physical activity and executive function. In addition, a Dutch cohort study found that the total time spent in team sports at ages 10 to 11 years was closely related to higher executive function, including behavior regulation and metacognition, compared to individual sports participation in children (12). Similarly, a meta-analysis showed that football training was positively related to attention, inhibitory control, and working memory in children and adolescents, indicating positive effects on cognitive performance (13). This evidence supports that an active, interactive environment of team play may stimulate cognitive processing, enhancing child growth and development (12, 14). Although interest in team sports and cognitive function has increased, research in this area remains limited. Further studies are needed to examine different stages of childhood and adolescence and a wider range of team sports.

Team Sports and Academic Performance in Children and Adolescents

Since team sports are associated with improved cognitive abilities, they may also have a positive influence on children's learning and academic performance. In particular, executive functions, such as attention, working memory, and inhibitory control, have been shown to be significant predictors of academic performance in children, as they support essential cognitive and self-regulation processes that underlie successful learning outcomes (6, 15). A previous study found that sports team participation was significantly associated with a higher mean GPA in high school students compared to those who do not participate on sports teams (16). Samarasinghe and colleagues also observed significant relationships

between sports team participation and class attendance and homework completion in adolescents, supporting the benefits of sports team involvement on better academic performance (17). In addition, there was an interesting evidence from a meta-analysis reported that sports participation during school hours and at a moderate dose (1-2 hours per week) was more beneficial for academic performance compared to no sports or a high dose of sports (≥ 3 hours per week), suggesting that a moderate amount of sports participation could be used to promote academic performance in children and adolescents (18). Furthermore, recent data from the Longitudinal Study of Australian Children showed that team sports participation was associated with reduced absenteeism, better performance on attention and working memory, and being awarded the Higher School Certificate (19).

Conclusion

In conclusion, participation in team sports plays an important role in supporting the physical, cognitive, and academic development of children and adolescents. Previous research showed that team sports contribute to improvements in not only physical fitness but also executive functions such as attention, self-control, and problem-solving. By combining evidence specifically related to team-based sports, this review highlights their unique developmental value beyond general physical activity. This focus is meaningful since many previous studies have examined broader types of physical activity or mixed-age groups rather than focusing on team sports during childhood. Therefore, future research should further investigate age-specific and long-term effects of team sports participation to better understand their role in promoting healthy and well-rounded development.

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